

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COFFEE INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *It is often claimed that an organization's greatest asset is its workforce. The most important task that every employer is currently executing is luring, protecting, and keeping them in order to fulfill the organization's objective. The goal of all human resources specialists and business leaders is to keep the best people in the company. So, business organizations now believe that keeping current employees on the job is more cost effective than hiring, onboarding, and training new ones. The organization's difficult challenge is employee retention. This study placed a strong emphasis on employee retention tactics. The organization's greatest asset is its workforce. Management should focus on ensuring employee satisfaction if it wants to keep talented and devoted workers in the company. Learn the causes of employee turnover so you can stop it. The goal of this study is to demonstrate how important staff retention is in the modern workplace, as well as the potential consequences for the business and the sector if leaders do not recognize the issue and take prompt action.*

Keywords: *Employee Retention, Employee Turnover Causes, and Employee Retention Techniques.*

INTRODUCTION

An organisation is a gathering where people from various backgrounds get together and collaborate to achieve a shared objective. Employees are those people who work for an organisation to support their families. Since each person contributes their time, knowledge, skills, and abilities to the success of the company, they are viewed as the lifeblood of the enterprise. The goal of all human resources specialists and business leaders is to keep the best people in the company. So, business organisations now believe that keeping current employees on the job is more cost-effective than hiring, onboarding, and training new ones. Every organisation spends considerable effort and resources on new hires. They set up training and help the individual grow in order to compete on an equal footing with the organization's current personnel. When these skilled workers quit their jobs, it is estimated that the organisation will suffer a significant loss. In this scenario, initiatives will be taken to ensure employee retention so they stay with the company for a longer amount of time (Swaroop & Sudhir, 2019).

FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE RETENTION

- **Recognizing Employee Skill:** Employee skill, knowledge, and competencies are crucial and can be viewed as the business house's assets. A balance between an employee's aim and the organization's goal will be established through regular

awards and recognition of employee success. The morale of the employee towards their work and organization will rise as a result of these kinds of initiatives.

- **Learning and Working Culture:** Depending on the organisational culture, each employee chooses whether to remain on work or leave. It is crucial for a business to be sensitive to the employees' learning and working cultures if it wants to retain its workforce. Building strong and pleasant relationships between management and employees will be greatly aided by providing a comfortable workplace.
- **Work Flexibility:** In the current environment, every firm views job flexibility as one of the most effective methods for keeping staff on board. Also, people look for businesses that use flexible scheduling, work sharing, flexible leave, and flexible locations. Employers and employees collaborate to accomplish the organization's goals when these gaps are bridged with the proper strategies. Also, it keeps employees loyal to the organisation.
- **Training and Career Development:** Workers are a business's most valuable resource since their performance determines whether the organisation succeeds or fails. As a result, organisations invest heavily in the training and development of their workforce. Training is a crucial component for job advancement.
- **Compensation and Benefits:** Profit maximisation is the primary organisational goal, and every person joins an organisation in order to advance their financial and social position. Before joining any organisation, people carefully analyse all factors, with the wage package coming in first. So, a firm that implements sound pay policies can draw in and keep talented individuals.
- **Communication:** Maintaining staff requires effective communication. There are four communication tools that boost worker retention.
 1. Regularly gathering with employees
 2. It is important to provide regular feedback to employees based on their performance.
 3. Having a duty to pursue ongoing education and professional development
 4. Conduct regular stay interviews.

DIFFICULTIES IN EMPLOYEE RETENTION:

Although management has some control over the rate at which employees leave the company and is able to keep talent within the company, they are unable to completely limit employee turnover. There are many difficulties in this field.

- **Financial Dissatisfaction:** Companies will adhere to the salary budget, which can be increased up to a point but not past it. When an employee is unwilling to make concessions and has very high compensation expectations that exceed the budget, retention becomes an issue.
- **There are many work opportunities:** Talented people face fierce competition on the job market. Companies go to great lengths to steal those abilities from their rivals. The draws more employees to the offers that the other company is offering and quit their job.
- **Hiring the Wrong Person:** Recruiting is a crucial part of creating a great organisation for the future. The basis for that future will be laying the proper person for the job. The likelihood of a job candidate telling any form of untruth during an interview is considerable; it is the HR's responsibility to make the best choice in this situation. because a poorly performing individual may eventually quit their position and cannot perform well.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Gorde, 2020) This study demonstrates the growing significance of employee retention in the workplace. It draws attention to the causes of the high turnover rate and the costs this behavior incurs for the business. This study briefly discusses the numerous contexts in which employee retention tactics are put into practice, such as the work environment, work culture, salary negotiation, compensation management, rewards and recognition, leadership, and the interaction between staff members and management. Hence, by implementing retention tactics and providing various welfare measures, the firm can teach certain practices that encourage employees to work well.

(Senthil Kumar & Jayesh, 2022) Their study has given readers a better grasp of the resources for inspiring and retaining employees using the best practices. These tactics help the businesses to reduce employee churn, management time, productivity loss, the expense of onboarding new employees, work interruptions, etc. Salary and corporate culture are significant factors in why employees leave a company. Every business must continue to implement an effective compensation plan and foster an environment that encourages employees to stick around. By implementing several strategies, including employee involvement, flexible scheduling, work-life balance, work from home, etc., it is possible to observe an increase in staff retention. Hence, if these procedures are primarily used in a company, employee turnover will be reduced. The goal of this study remained to assist IT firms in developing effective HR policies to increase employee engagement.

(A Study of Employee Retention, 2019) The study reveals that majority of those surveyed believed that the workplace (facility, workplace, and campus) had an impact on employee job satisfaction and, ultimately, employee retention. It was shown that the majority of employees value supervision, direction, and guidance within the workplace. The majority of respondents believe that benefit programmes including those for health and welfare, retirement benefits, and paid time off help them balance their work and personal lives.

The respondents believe that the work-life programmes (family support and personal assistance) are enabling them to maintain a balance between their personal and professional lives. Career opportunities have been demonstrated to increase employee happiness. Motivating others requires effective leadership.

(Numanovich & Abbosxonovich, 2020) Learning from this study's sample of 50 accounts will help us verify that one of the biggest problems in the IT industry is retention. For HR managers, employee retention has evolved into the work with the most facets and challenges. As stated in the, the privatisation of the IT sector has caused a number of factors that have contributed to the loss of important employees. Employee retention now necessitates offering stress relievers, deserving acknowledgment, just treatment, and growth opportunities. Employees would want to work somewhere that maintains their interest and growth in harmony with the work and organisational goals because compensation is no longer a strategy for retention.

(Mathimaran & Kumar, 2017) The results of the study reveal that specific factors are important in influencing an employee's decision to quit or stay in an organisation, which is important given the growing necessity for firms to retain their best people in the face of competition. A competitive compensation package, job security, recognition and reward for good performance, and training and development are a few examples of these factors. Nonetheless, when creating a retention policy, the significance of other factors shouldn't be underestimated. The high incidence of employee turnover in our diverse firms can only be improved and decreased by a thorough blending of inner and extrinsic incentive factors.

(Pavithra & Thirukumaran, 2018) The results of a three-month study on employee retention strategies at Philips Electronics India Limited, conducted in Chennai, were examined, and it was determined that most respondents were content with the company's health and safety policies. According to the report, Philips Electronics should develop and implement new retention strategies to improve the organization's potential for growth and to lighten employees' workloads. According to the report, the majority of employees

thought their pay packages were inadequate and recommended improving the workplace atmosphere.

(Jain, 2011) Retaining the competent and talented employees is one of the most contentious concerns in the business sector in today's competitive and dynamic business environment. The human resource department is viewed as the torch bearer for the continued existence and success of organisations. Retaining qualified and competent workers who can contribute to the growth and reputation of organisations is therefore of utmost importance to those firms. But, the aggressive competitors' generous compensation packages and other incentives for important individuals have made it difficult for the firms to keep hold of them. Such a situation necessitates the involvement of HR experts, academics, researchers, and other policy makers in the development and implementation of retention measures that would not only recruit and keeping talented and competent workers on staff will not only help firms perform better and become more competitive globally.

(Sinha et al., 2022) their research reveals that Employee retention is important for a number of reasons, including the difficulty and time involved in hiring, the need to keep top performers, the likelihood that departing employees may join competitors, and the fact that long-tenured employees are more devoted to management and the company. Workers should be given challenging tasks, a conflict-free work atmosphere, the best candidate should be recruited, and employees should feel valued. These include the effort put forward by the employee, success-based pay increments, and making the compensation and other requirements crystal clear during the interview. Being a company's most precious asset, its human resources must be maintained with the utmost care.

(Raj & Brindha, 2017) Talented people stick around when an approach is taken that fosters trust and supports lifetime careers. When people believe that the possibilities and experiences they have with their current employment extend their career options, they are more likely to stay. Workers must feel valued and appreciated, receive feedback, have opportunity for professional development, have options for balancing work and personal obligations, and have faith and confidence in their managers. All of these retention tactics are useful for employers who wish to retain staff members on board and reduce turnover expenses. It's difficult to manage retention in your company effectively.

RESEARCH GAP:

Following a review of the literature, it was discovered that all research studies on employee retention techniques focused on the industrial sector rather than the plantation

sector. It is one of the top industries in the nation that supports economic expansion. So, I decided that it would be worth while to take on projects in this sector and chose Tata Coffee Ltd.

AN OUTLINE OF THE PROBLEM

To keep their workers for a longer amount of time, businesses offer the best amenities. It has been determined that there are a few elements influencing employees to remain with the company for a longer period of time.

NECESSITY OF THE STUDY

The study aims to define Tata Coffee Ltd. staff retention. The purpose of the study is to carefully examine the factors driving employees to remain with the company for a longer period of time. Through this, an effort is made to comprehend employee perceptions of the business' staff retention efforts.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To analyse numerous aspects influencing Tata Coffee Ltd.'s staff retention efforts, to comprehend how employees perceive those strategies, and to provide appropriate recommendations based on the findings.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The survey will assist in determining how each employee feels about the methods used by the business to keep talented individuals. The study will assist the business in developing the best concepts to meet employee expectations in light of the present environment so that it can draw in young and talented people. Also, the study provides comprehensive information for students who wish to conduct their own research on employee retention.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The overall approach utilised to integrate the various study components in order to effectively address the issue is known as research design. By the use of research design, a rough outline of how research should be carried out can be created. In this study, the problem is assessed using an exploratory and descriptive research approach.

In order to select the respondents, a non-probability sampling technique is used.

Sampling Method: A method for choosing responders from the study's general population is sampling. The study used the convenience sampling methodology.

Sample Size: There were 51 respondents in total for this survey.

Sampling Frame: The source from which respondents are selected is the sampling frame.

HYPOTHESIS:

To fulfil the objective of the study following statistical hypotheses were constructed and tested subsequently.

H1	H ₀	There was no significant mean difference in economic factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
	H ₁	There exists a significant mean difference in economic factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
H2	H ₀	There was no significant mean difference in developmental factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
	H ₁	There exists a significance mean difference in developmental factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
H3	H ₀	There was no significant mean difference in work environmental factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
	H ₁	There exists a significance mean difference in work environmental factor score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
H4	H ₀	There was no significant mean difference in overall employee retention strategies score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
	H ₁	There exists a significance mean difference in overall employee retention strategies score as one of the employee retention strategies among demographic information.
H5	H ₀	The level of perception of employees towards employee retention strategies at Tata Coffee Ltd Pollibetta follows uniform distribution.
	H ₁	The level of perception of employees towards retention strategies at Tata coffee Ltd Pollibetta follows uneven distribution.
H6	H ₀	The perception towards employee retention strategies and demographic classification are independent.
	H ₁	The perception towards employee retention strategies and demographic classification are dependent.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Demographic description of respondents (N=51)

CHARACTERISTICS	VARIABLE	NUMBER	%
GENDER	Male	37	73
	Female	14	27
AGE	Below 30 years	5	10
	30 to 40 years	13	26
	40 to 50 years	14	27
	Above 50 years	19	37
EDUCATIONAL	PUC	6	12
	Bachelor degree	26	51
	Masterdegree	14	27
	Diploma	5	10

INTERPRETATION**Gender:**

To test H1toH4T-test was used and computation made were tabulated in Table

Group Statistics						
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
Economic factor	Male	36	32.92	3.901	-1.690	.097
	Female	15	34.87	3.357		
Developmental factor	Male	36	31.36	4.618	-1.603	.115
	Female	15	33.60	4.356		
WEF	Male	36	32.56	3.798	-1.620	.112
	Female	15	34.40	3.460		
Overall	Male	36	96.83	11.380	-1.820	.075
	Female	15	102.87	9.141		

From the above table following inference is drawn.

- Since $P=0.097 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in economic factor score between male and female employees at 5% level of significance.
- Since $P=0.115 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in developmental factor score between male and female employees at 5% level of significance.

- Since $P=0.112 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in work environmental factor score between male and female employees at 5% level of significance.
- Since $P=0.075 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in overall factor score between male and female employees at 5% level of significance.

Age Group:

To test H_1 to H_4 One Way Anova was used and computation made was tabulated in the following table.

ANOVA						
		Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Economic	Between Groups	101.360	3	33.787	2.523	.069
	Within Groups	629.385	47	13.391		
	Total	730.745	50			
Developmental	Between Groups	147.873	3	49.291	2.526	.069
	Within Groups	917.108	47	19.513		
	Total	1064.980	50			
WEF	Between Groups	25.965	3	8.655	.596	.621
	Within Groups	682.544	47	14.522		
	Total	708.510	50			
Overall	Between Groups	694.557	3	231.519	2.017	.124
	Within Groups	5393.600	47	114.757		
	Total	6088.157	50			

From the above table following inference is drawn.

- Since $P= 0.069 >0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in economic factor score between age group of employees at 5% level of significance.

Post hoc test indicates that there exists significant mean difference in economic factor score between 30 to 40 years and above 50 years age group employees and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels.

- Since $P=0.069 >0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in developmental factor score between age group of employees at 5% level of significance.

Post hoc test indicates that there exists significant mean difference in developmental factor score between 30 to 40 years and 40 to 50 years, 30 to 40 years and above 50 years and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels.

- Since $P = 0.621 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in work environmental factor score between age group of employees at 5% level of significance.
- Since $P = 0.124 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in over all factor score between age group of employees at 5% level of significance.

Posthoc test indicates that there exists significant mean difference in overall employee retention strategies score between 30 to 40 years and above 50 years and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels.

Education Qualification:

To test H1 to H4 One Way Anova was used and computation made was tabulated in the following table.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Economic factor	Between Groups	23.703	3	7.901	.525	.667
	With in Groups	707.042	47	15.043		
	Total	730.745	50			
Developmental factor	Between Groups	51.028	3	17.009	.788	.506
	With in Groups	1013.952	47	21.573		
	Total	1064.980	50			
WEF	Between Groups	56.316	3	18.772	1.353	.269
	With in Groups	652.194	47	13.876		
	Total	708.510	50			
Overall	Between Groups	336.771	3	112.257	.917	.440
	With in Groups	5751.386	47	122.370		
	Total	6088.157	50			

From the above table following inference is drawn:

- Since $P = 0.667 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in economic factor score between education qualification of employees at 5% level of significance.

- Since $P=0.506 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in developmental factor score between education qualifications of employees at 5% level of significance.
- Since $P=0.269 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in work environmental factor score between education qualification of employees at 5% level of significance.
- Since $P=0.440 > 0.05$ the test was not significant, that is there was no significant mean difference in overall factor score between education qualification of employees at 5% level of significance.

To test H5 it is customary to present the norm table for economic factor and then apply Chi Square test

Economic Group					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Perent
Valid	Average	6	11.8	11.8	11.8
	Above Average	45	88.2	88.2	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Calculated Chi Square value: 28.32 Tabulated Chi square value: 5.991

- Since calculated Chi square value is greater than table value the test was significant at 5% levels that is among 51 employees 6 (11.8%) were at average level of perception towards economic factors of retention strategies of the company. And 45 (88.2%) were at above average level of perception and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels. To test H5 it is customary to present the norm table for developmental factor and then apply ChiSquare test.

Developmental group					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BelowAverage	7	13.7	13.7	13.7
	Average	35	68.6	68.6	82.4
	AboveAverage	9	17.6	17.6	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Calculated ChiSquare value: 28.69

Tabulated Chisquare value: 5.991

- Since calculated Chi square value is greater than table value the test was significant at 5% levels that is among 51 employees 7 (13.7%) were at below average level of perception towards developmental factors of retention strategies of the company. And 35 (68.6%) were at average level of perception, 9 (17.6%) and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels.

To test H5 it is customary to present the norm table for work environmental factor and then apply Chi Square test.

WEF Group					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below Average	6	11.8	11.8	11.8
	Average	33	64.7	64.7	76.5
	Above Average	12	23.5	23.5	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Calculated Chi Square value: 23.63

Tabulated Chisquare value: 5.99z

- Since calculated Chi square value is greater than table value the test was significant at 5% levels that is among 51 employees 6 (11.8%) were at below average level of perception towards work environmental factors of retention strategies of the company. And 33 (64.7%) were at average level of perception, 12 (23.5%) and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels.

To test H5 it is customary to present the norm table for overall retention strategies and then apply Chi Square test.

Overall Group					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below Average	6	11.8	11.8	11.8
	Average	36	70.6	70.6	82.4
	Above Average	9	17.6	17.6	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Calculated Chi Square value: 32.1 Tabulated Chi square value: 5.991

- Since calculated Chi square value is greater than table value the test was significant at 5% levels that is among 51 employees 6 (11.8%) were at below average level of perception towards overall factors of retention strategies of the company. And 36(70.6%) were at average level of perception, 9 (17.6%) and it was found to be statistically significant at 5% levels

To test H6 Chi Square test for independence of at tribute was used.

To test H6 Chi Square test was used and computations made are tabulated in the table.

Chi-Square Tests (Age group)			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.589a	6	.270
Like lihood Ratio	11.536	6	.073
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.553	1	.059
No of Valid Cases	51		

- Since $P = 0.27 > 0.05$ the test was not significant at 5% level that is over retention strategies level and age group are independent at 5% level of significance that is the age difference has no impact on the perception of employee towards overall retention strategy of the company.
- With the age group 50 and above years 77.8% of employee"s perception is at average level about the retention strategies of the company.

To test H6 Chi Square test was used and computations made are tabulated in the table.

Chi-Square Tests (Gender)			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.502a	2	.174
Like lihood Ratio	5.110	2	.078
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.096	1	.078
No of Valid Cases	51		

- Since $P = 0.174 > 0.05$ the test was not significant at 5% level that is over retention strategies level and gender group are independent at 5% level of significance thatisthe gender difference has no impact on the perception of employee towards overall retention strategy of the company.
- With the gender group 73.3% of employee"s perception is at average level about the retention strategies of the company.

To test H6 Chi Square test was used and computations made are tabulated in the table.

Chi -Square Tests (Education qualification)			
	Value	Df	Asymp.Sig.(2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.919a	6	.244
Like lihood Ratio	7.698	6	.261
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.538	1	.060
No of Valid Cases	51		

- Since $P = 0.244 > 0.05$ the test was not significant at 5% level that is over retention strategies level and education qualification group are independent at 5% level of significance that is the qualification difference has no impact on the perception of employee to wards overall retention strategy of the company.
- With the education qualification group 83.5% of employee's perception is at average level about the retention strategies of the company.

FINDINGS

The survey found that all of Tata Coffee Limited's employees have a tendency to stay with the company because of the firm's economic and developmental tenets and the favourable working environment it provides. The management was advised to do the following based on the study.

- In order to improve employee productivity and increase employee loyalty to the organisation, human resource management activities must include talent and knowledge management components.
- The company's overall compensation plan needs to be attractive so that, in addition to keeping experienced personnel, management can also recruit talented people from the competitive talent market.
- In order to encourage employees to feel appreciated and contribute to the team, management should provide them with opportunities to practise based on their interests and expertise.

CONCLUSION

The study was focused on three crucial variables: economic, developmental, and work environment variables. According to the researcher's findings, respondent perception of all elements are significant, and demographic differences amongst respondents have little bearing on the company's retention strategy. According to the study, there is no discernible mean difference between all parameters and responder demographics. The researcher's advice will enable the organisation to carry out its tasks even more effectively.

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